

IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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Abstract. *The article discusses the main approaches to improving the management of physical culture and sports propaganda among young people of the younger generation is of great importance in the development of physical culture sports and a healthy lifestyle in modern conditions.*

Keywords: *sport, physical culture, health, management, modern technologies.*

In the modern world, there is an increase in the economic and political function of the sphere of physical culture and sports, along with its social significance. The development of physical culture and sports has a positive impact on all spheres of society, increasing human potential. Creating additional factors for successful socio economic development In this regard, it is particularly important to improve the existing approaches to the management of physical culture.

There are a number of problems in the development of physical culture and sports:

- Insufficient involvement of the population in systematic physical education;
- Insufficient development of the material base and infrastructure of physical culture and sports;
- Insufficient number of professional coaching staff;
- Lack of active promotion of physical culture and sports as an integral part of a healthy lifestyle, including taking care of the health of the future generation;

The propaganda direction is of decisive importance in the development of the sphere of physical culture and sports. Propaganda in the life of people's activities has various forms, for example (oral, printed, visual, etc.) dissemination and clarification of ideas, teachings, views, theories that affect the consciousness and mood of a wide range of people.

The promotion of physical culture implies purposeful activities to disseminate knowledge in the field of physical culture and sports, as well as to introduce the population to systematic physical culture and sports, as well as to maintain a healthy lifestyle in modern living conditions.

An important role in its successful achievement of the main objectives of propaganda is played by the correct formulation of information propaganda. To do this, it is extremely necessary to increase the level of a healthy lifestyle of people among the population; education of the need for the approval of a healthy lifestyle, the use of physical culture in the mode of work and rest.

By itself the expression and concept of the word healthy lifestyle of people should include such conditions as:

- Regular physical education classes;
- Rejection of bad habits and addictions;
- Balanced nutrition;
- Compliance with the daily routine;
- Rational combination of physical activity with intellectual work;
- Conducting classes in ecologically clean areas (urban park, mountainous areas, etc.).

In other words, physical education does not guarantee positive results if any of these conditions are not met. Only compliance with an integrated approach to the implementation of all the principles of a healthy lifestyle entails the acquisition of moral and physical comfort. Thus, physical education is only one of the sides of the process of educating a harmoniously developed personality, which should occupy a fairly significant part in the schedule of the daily routine of a modern person. In our modern conditions of life and time, this problem has become more urgent, as the number of "office" workers who lead a sedentary lifestyle has increased. These people spend the whole day in a stuffy room and a confined space, are often in a state of high stress, and also travel by personal or official vehicles (all this contributes to the development of hypodynamia and chronic hypoxia in combination with instability of blood pressure and high lability of the nervous system). Even a passion for fitness and a visit to the gym after the end of the working day against the background of professional fatigue does not relieve the severity of the problem – such unsystematic loads only aggravate the chronic fatigue syndrome, which leads to a negative effect on the body. Physical culture and sports are one of the main areas of satisfaction of vital human needs in motor activity, in which the harmonious formation of personality is ensured. Physical culture creates the necessary prerequisites and conditions for maintaining a healthy lifestyle of a person, an essential component of which is the organization of motor activity. The maintenance of the body contributes to the increase of working capacity, creative activity, physical improvement, preservation and health of the younger generation. The adoption of regulatory legal documents in our republic in the field of physical culture and sports allows us to clearly identify. Goals and objectives of the direction in the field of promotion of physical culture and sports distribute the powers of responsibility, as well as determining the basis of interaction between authorities. The draft constitutional law recently published for public discussion includes an article that enshrines the state's obligation to create conditions for the development of physical culture and sports, spiritual and moral education of children of the younger generation. In my opinion, it is very timely and relevant, since attention to the health of the state is indirectly reflected in the development of physical culture and sports, one can even say in the need for the level of involvement of the population in mass sports. Accompanied by developments in digital technology have seriously changed our way of life in modern conditions. On the one hand, one can observe how the lifestyle is rapidly changing, on the other hand, there is also a negative side of progress. The widespread penetration of digital technologies into our lives is accompanied by a decrease in people's physical activity. And this affects absolutely any category of people and they spend more and more time in gadgets. Adults prefer the activity of watching news on social networks. At the same time, it is a well-known fact that there is a connection between human health and physical activity, which should be an obligatory element of a healthy human life. It is obvious that regular sports activities affect not only the physical condition of a person, but also the psychological well-being. Nevertheless, in our country there is a decrease in physical activity of the population and this is a consequence of the deterioration of public health. Health determines the quality of life and it is important to pay attention that sports and physical culture are not only a healthy lifestyle, but also the development of endurance and patience. Therefore, it is necessary to actively involve people in physical education. This, in turn, determines a holistic attitude to one's health, because physical activity as an element of a healthy lifestyle solves such tasks as disease prevention. And everyone knows that it is always easier to prevent a disease than to treat it. The World Health Organization, constantly studying the health issues of the population of various countries, makes arguments in

favor of constant physical education of the population. Among them are the prevention and treatment of non-communicable diseases, such as cardiovascular diseases, and the reduction of symptoms of depression and anxiety. Physical activity contributes to the improvement of thinking, learning and critical assessment skills, and the younger generation as a whole increases the overall level of well-being in modern conditions. Measures for the development of physical culture and sports are defined in the development strategy of the New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026. The purpose of this strategy is to increase the number of citizens of the country regularly engaged in physical education and sports. In increasing the coverage of physical education classes among the population, and according to preliminary calculations, this is up to 6 million citizens (42% of whom are the younger generation) and this will help in the modern world. Currently, the regulation of relations in this area is regulated by the Law "On Physical Culture and Sports", the recently signed Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve and popularize physical culture and sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the Concept of Development of Physical Culture and Sports until 2025.

It should be noted that the law "On Physical Culture and Sports" provides for the implementation of state programs for the development of physical culture and sports, but the area of responsibility for such an important area of social policy is dispersed among various institutions. Therefore, in today's realities of intensive reforms, the task of developing physical culture and sports should go directly to the state, as a guarantor of the implementation and inviolability of the reforms initiated in this direction. Therefore, the expedient inclusion of norms in the constitution creates the necessary conditions for the development of physical culture and sports in the future. And this will contribute to a wider involvement of the population, especially young people, women and children of the younger generation, in physical culture and sports and will serve to form a healthy lifestyle among the population in the modern living conditions of citizens of our country in the future.

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